

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DUNCAN****FIRST NAME: JOHN****PROGRAM CODE: MTSD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 9%

The author used the following software: MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. One main distinction between qualitative research projects and quantitative research projects is that:
 - Quantitative research involves a deep understanding of social settings or activity as viewed by the participants; qualitative research examines cause-effect relationships.
 - Qualitative research examines events over an ongoing period of time as they cause changes to society; quantitative research examines a fixed period of time to determine how an event evolved in a society.

Qualitative research involves a deep understanding of social settings or activities as viewed by the participants; quantitative research examines cause-effect relationships.¹

Quantitative research is a type of qualitative research that focuses specifically on causal relationships within a specifically designated aspect of a society.

2. What would be an acceptable number of entries for a bibliography in a doctoral dissertation?

At least 400, with a minimum of 10% being journal articles.

As few as 100 if at least 40 of them are journal articles.

100-150, with 20% being journal articles.²

250-300, with 25% being journal articles.

3. Pure research is defined by *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* as:

research that addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any practical applications.³

research that stays rigidly aligned to the topic with no deviation or exploration of follow-on information.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition, (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 135.

² EUCLID. "Thesis or Dissertation Evaluation Form" (Bangui: Euclid University, 2023).

³ Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, editing, and Publishing (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 29.

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- research that terminates with a provable conclusion but does not provide recommendations for future research.
 - research following the dictates of the Esom Committee for Pure Research.
4. What is the difference between a secondary source and a tertiary source?
- A secondary source is an original study or project with the results removed, and a tertiary source is a review of a study written by a peer.
 - A tertiary source is an article written for broad audiences, and a secondary source is an article written in a scholastic journal reviewed by peers.⁴**
 - Tertiary sources are also considered the “literature of the field” while the secondary sources are projects done by leading researchers in the field, but not directly related to the current project.
 - Secondary sources are not considered “scholastic,” but are still useful for background information, while tertiary sources are used to find other points of view within the field.
5. According to Bloomberg, Dale and Volpe, (2019) introduction & overview, research sample, overview of information needed, research design, data collection methods, data analysis and synthesis, ethical considerations, issues of trustworthiness, limitations and delimitations, and chapter summary are all required for which part of the dissertation?

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 36-37.

Chapter 3, methodology⁵

- Chapter 2, literature review
- Chapter 6, conclusion
- Chapter 1, introduction

6. Bloomberg, Dale and Volpe (2019) maintain that the methodology that is associated with the social sciences, including folklore, anthropology, history, urban development, education, linguistics, communication, culture studies, and sociology is:

- Phenomenology
- Narrative Inquiry
- The Critical Genres

 Ethnography⁶

7. What, according to Turabian et al. (2018), do you add to an argument to ensure that the relevance of your statement is clear to the reader?

 A warrant⁷

- A disclaimer
- A citation
- An explanation

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 80-81.

⁶ Ibid., 249.

⁷ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 62.

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8. What section of your dissertation should ensure that readers have a clear idea of your claims, ensure they understand the importance of it and suggest future related research?

- Literature review
- Introduction
- Conclusion**⁸
- Findings

9. According to Turabian et al. (2018), any study that will involve human subjects, record the private behavior of human subjects, or obtain identifying information about living human subjects must be approved by the:

- Academic Ethics Committee (AEC)
- Institutional Review Board (IRB)**⁹
- Educational Evaluation Board (EEB)
- International Review Board (IRB)

10. Bloomberg and Volpe (2019) state that “Illustrating in great detail how a culture-sharing group works and lives is the final product of...”

- a phenomenological study
- a narrative inquiry

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⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 110.

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⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 226.

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an ethnographic study¹⁰

a critical genres study

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

[EUCLID](#). "Thesis or Dissertation Evaluation Form." (Bangui: Euclid University, 2023).

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Bloomberg, Dale, and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 282.